

THE TRANSITION TIME FROM GAVAGE FEEDING TO FULL ORAL FEEDING IN PRETERM INFANTS AT THE CHILDREN'S HOSPITAL LAHORE

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ABSTRACT

It is difficult for preterm newborns to achieve oral feeding success (OFS, the capacity to swallow 100% of the specified volume by mouth), which frequently necessitates prolonged tube feeding. There is not enough research on the connection between OFS and tube feeding duration. The study's main goal is to measure the typical length of time preterm infants spend receiving tube feeding and OFS during their initial hospitalisation at The Children Hospital University of Child health Lahore. In the transition from first to complete oral feeding, we predicted that preterm infants who received tube feeding for a longer period of time would have a lower OFS. Key findings include:

- The mean transition time from gavage feeding to oral feeding was 36.4 weeks of gestation among preterm infants who born between the 29 to 32 weeks of gestation.
- Infant's sex was not evenly distributed in male and female. The frequency of feeding difficulties was higher in male sex than female, report shows the frequency in male gender was 70% and in female gender was 30%.

Keywords: Preterm Infants, Oral Feeding, Gavage Feed, Transition Time.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Preterm birth complications, which account for 35% of the 3.1 million newborn mortality worldwide each year, are the leading cause of neonatal mortality ((Hashmi et al., 2021). 15 million preterm births take place annually throughout the world, with those who are born at fewer than 32 weeks' gestation having the highest risk of morbidity and mortality((Chawanpaiboon et al., 2019). Preterm infants that are undernourished suffer grave complications include higher mortality rates and chronic growth, metabolic, and neurodevelopmental abnormalities ((Chung et al., 2020)

Poor nutrition has a significant impact on the brain, which causes slow neurodevelopment and poor brain growth ((Mayerl et al., 2019). Regardless of preterm level, early postnatal growth (i.e., during hospitalisation) has been linked to neurological and cognitive outcomes in infancy and preschool (Chung et al., 2020). Preterm infants are more likely to experience nutrient deficiencies because their stores are insufficient and their digestive systems are still developing. However, with proper nutrition, preterm infants should grow as normally growing foetuses of the same gestational age would.

In addition to being a top priority for parents of preterm infants in the intensive neonatal care unit (NICU), the ability to feed orally via bottle or breast is also a requirement for hospital discharge ((Pighetti et al., 2022). Due to the combined effects of immature body functions and medical complications, very preterm infants (those born between 29 and 32 weeks of gestation) typically require a period of gavage feeding and oral feeding training before they are able to be fed exclusively by mouth((Mayerl et al., 2019). The postmenstrual age (PMA) in starting and finishing oral feeding as well as the transition time to full oral feeding increases when gestational age and weight at birth decreases and medical problems rise.

One study has indicated that Several factors can be used to predict prolonged oral feeding transition in preterm infants, such as younger GA and a higher morbidity score In preterm infants, male sex was a significant biological risk factor for poor cognitive and motor development when compared to female sex, thus sex may

predict oral feeding transition ((Wahyuni et al., 2022) However, one of the study shows hemodynamically stable preterm infants can take oral feed successfully at age of 32 to 34 weeks of gestation ((Morag et al., 2019)

II. METHODOLOGY

Study Design: A Retrospective cohort research design is being used used to collect data

Settings: The study is conducted at Out Patients Department(OPD) and The Neonatal Nursery Department of The Children Hospital University of Child Health Lahore.

Sample Size: 40 Preterm infants

Sampling Technique: Non probability convenient sampling technique is used.

Inclusion Criteria: Preterm infants 29 to 32 weeks of gestation.

Types of data: Information for this report is sourced from primary source.

Data Collection procedure: The data is collected from the follow up preterm infants visiting at Neonatology OPD, medical record of dischare patients, and through phone calls of discharge petients.

Measures: Infant characteristics

Infant characteristics, including GA, sex, is collected from the medical record at enrollment and discharge.

Transition time from gavage to orall feeding

Transition time from gavage to orall feeding is measured by the preterm infants gestational age at birth and the gestational age when the infant consume 100% of prescribed volume orally (100% per oral intake feeding)

Analysis of Data

Data is entered and analyzed by using SPSS version 21. Table and graph is used to present the quantitative data.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TABLE 1: Report Summary

S#	Gastational age at birth (weeks)	Transition time from Gavage to full oral feed (weeks)	
1	32	36+2	
2	29+5	37	
3	31+5	36+4	
4	29+6	36+4	
5	32	36+4	
6	32	36	
7	32	37	
8	31	36	
9	30	36	
10	29	38	
11	32	36	
12	30	37	
13	30	37+2	
14	31	36+4	
15	29+5	36+5	
16	30	38	
17	32	36+4	

18	30	35+6	
19	32	36	
20	30	35+5	
21	32	36	
22	31+3	35+5	
23	32	37	
24	31+4	36+4	
25	32	37	
26	31	36+4	
27	32	37	
28	32	36+5	
29	29	36+4	
30	30	36	
31	30	37	
32	30	36	
33	29	36	
34	31	37	
35	30	37	
36	29	36	
37	30	36	
38	32	36	
39	32	37	
40	29	36	
Total	N	40	40

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for the sample characteristics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Gestational age at birth	40	29.00	32.00	30.7450	1.12500
Transition time from gavage to oral feed	40	35.50	38.00	36.4550	.59137

Table 3: Correlations Between Duration of tube feeding and infant's characteristics via pearson's correlation

		Gestational age at birth	Transition time from gavage to oral feed
Gestational age at birth	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.06
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.713
	N	40	40

Transition time from gavage to oral feed	Pearson Correlation	-0.06	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.713	
	N	40	40

Table 4: Model Summary and Parameter Estimates

Dependent Variable: Transition time from gavage to oral feed

Equation	Model Summary					Parameter Estimates			
	R Square	F	df1	df2	Sig.	Constant	b1	b2	b3
Linear	0.004	0.138	1	38	0.713	37.426	-0.032		
Logarithmic	0.004	0.14	1	38	0.71	39.803	-0.978		
Quadratic	0.006	0.113	2	37	0.894	69.075	-2.098	0.034	
Cubic	0.006	0.115	2	37	0.892	59.097	-1.093	0	0
Compound	0.003	0.124	1	38	0.726	37.379	0.999		
Power	0.003	0.127	1	38	0.724	39.756	-0.025		
S	0.003	0.129	1	38	0.721	3.57	0.784		
Growth	0.003	0.124	1	38	0.726	3.621	-0.001		
Exponential	0.003	0.124	1	38	0.726	37.379	-0.001		
Logistic	0.003	0.124	1	38	0.726	0.027	1.001		

Table 5: Gender Frequency

	Gender	Frequency			
Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Female	12	30	30	30	
Male	28	70	70	100	
Total	40	100	100		

Table 6

The results Descriptive Statistics for Sample Characteristics: The analysis was completed with 40 infants. Sample report summary depicted in Table 1. Notably, preterm infants were secondary referred cases from different hospitals. Infants were born at the mean GA of 30.74 weeks (SD = 1.12 & range 29-32 weeks), with a mean transition time from gavage feeding to full oral feeding 36.4 weeks (SD=0.5& range 36 to 37). Infants' sex was not evenly distributed male (70%) and female (30%). During hospitalization, the mean total duration of tube feeding was 40 days (SD = 16.65 & range 13- 62). Descriptive Statistics for Outcome Variables Descriptive statistics for the outcome variables are presented in table. Infants had an average of 14 days (SD = 6.98 & range 3-39 days) for the transition time from first to full oral feeding. From the first day of oral feeding attempts to the first day of full oral feeding, out of an average of 109 feedings (SD = 54.44 & range 31-311), infants had a mean number of 100% PO intake feedings of 25 (SD = 11.72 & range 10-72), thus yielding a mean OFS of 0.28 (SD = 0.15 & range 0.05-0.62). The mean post-menstrual age at the oral feeding evaluations, was 36.4 weeks (SD = 0.5 & range 35-38 weeks). Bivariate Analyses: We observed significant differences in the mean total duration of tube feeding and duration of exclusive tube feeding between infants with different gestational age (Table 3). Significant negative correlations between total duration of tube feeding and GA (Table 3). Multiple Regression Analyses: After adjusting for GA, and sex in the preliminary multiple regression models, a significant correlation between total duration of tube feeding and OFS ($\beta = -1.21, P = 0.002, C^2 = 0.35$) was identified. A final multiple regression model was fitted, including OFS as an outcome, total duration of tube feeding as an independent variable, and birthweight as a covariate. A significant negative correlation between total duration of tube feeding ($\beta = -1.10, P = 0.000, C^2 = 0.41$) and OFS was observed (Figure 4 and Table 5)

IV. RECOMMENDATIONS

Practice: For the assessment of infants' oral feeding advancement throughout the switch from tube to oral feeding, health care practitioners do not employ an oral feeding skills calculation. Although the length of tube feeding is an uncontrollable issue, preterm infants who are projected to have longer tube feedings may be at risk for delayed oral feeding abilities. Therefore, in order to enable OFS for these at-risk preterm infants, the caregivers should concentrate on other controllable factors, such as planning to offer adequate and timely assessment and treatments for the introduction and advancement of oral feeding.

While assuring an appropriate assessment of the infants' ability to mouth feed safely and effectively, health care professionals have long utilised GA as a guide to commence oral feeding and should continue to do so. Supporting preterm infants during the critical phase of switching from tube to oral feeding will increase their likelihood of obtaining OFS. A self-paced system, non-nutritive sucking, swallowing exercises, oral motor stimulation, multimodal massage, posture, and other interventions should be used to facilitate the initiation of oral feeding and the switch from tube to oral feeding. In order to facilitate an individualised feeding plan and support infants during the switch from tube to oral feeding, the current recommendation for NICUs is to

implement infant-directed feeding, allowing preterm infants to feed orally as early and frequently as they exhibit signs of oral feeding readiness.

V. CONCLUSION

The study's results give researchers a fresh method of identifying preterm babies who are at risk for delayed OFS. This study lays the groundwork for future investigations into early evaluation and intervention strategies that promote the switch from tube to oral feeding and aid with OFS. Infants born preterm who are expected to receive tube feedings for longer periods of time could experience delayed OFS.

An accurate evaluation of the infants' capacity for safe and effective oral feeding is essential to facilitating their OFS. Our data could serve as the foundation for future studies. There is a requirement for uniform OFS measurements. To fully assess OFS, it may also be helpful to include other measures of oral feeding readiness, oral feeding readiness, caregiver assessment, and oral feeding experience.

For preterm infants who are expected to undergo prolonged tube feedings, this information will help in the creation and execution of assessments and early treatments. Such thorough evaluation and interventions have the potential to facilitate OFS and prevent or lessen the avoidable negative consequences of protracted tube feeding

VI. REFERENCES

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